

Compare and contrast Cutler and Miller (2005) with Anderson et al. (2022). How do these papers help us understand what caused the decline in the mortality since the mid-18th century?

(ES30083: Coursework)

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Compare and contrast Cutler and Miller (2005) with Anderson et al. (2022). How do these papers help us understand what caused the decline in the mortality since the mid-18th century?

Cutler and Miller (2005) (CM) and Anderson et al (2022) (ACR) attempt to explain the period between 1900 and 1940, when the US was experiencing its most rapid decline in mortality. In the UK, this period was slightly early, starting around 1860 (figure 1.1) and flattening out in the early 20th century. Similar trends in mortality occurred across Europe and North America (Cutler et al 2006). The UK’s trend coincides with an earlier adoption of clean water interventions compared with the US. They noted that the US mortality reduction started slightly later, but broadly followed a similar pattern. This paper also outlined several determinants of mortality that could explain this fall including nutrition, public health, urbanisation, vaccination, medical treatments, and improvements to early life factors. CM and ACR investigate the extent to which public health (more specifically clean water) interventions explain the steepest part of the mortality decline. Whilst these papers are similar in many ways, their conclusions, and implications on the cause of the mortality decline vary substantially. McKeown and Record (1962) argued that environmental change in the standard of living and sanitary reforms were key drivers of the mortality transformation, with resistance explaining no more than a third. Millward and Bell (1998) and Haines (2001) make a similar argument,

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics	Anderson et al	Cutler and Miller			Difference
		1900	1940	Average 1900 to 1940	
Female	50%	51%	51%	51%	-1%
Non-white	9%	11%	14%	13%	-4%
foreign	19%	22%	11%	17%	3%
under 15	26%	31%	21%	26%	0%
15 to 44	53%	53%	51%	52%	1%
45 +	22%	17%	28%	22%	-1%

with the former emphasising the rate of nutrition and standard of living improvements. Fogel (1997, 2004) also explored the role of nutrition, particularly in economic growth alongside reduced mortality. Several papers have emphasised the urban environment and pointed to a substantial decline in urban mortality, highlighting the role of clean water interventions rather than nutrition as these were focused on cities. Caine and Rotella (2001) found that a 1% increase in sanitation expenditure led to nearly 3% decline in deaths in the average sized city. Costa and Khan (2015) further investigated this relationship particularly in areas of high mortality.

ACR and CM are quite similar in many ways. Both papers use the same set of data from 1900 to 1936, with ACR using additional data for the years 1937 to 1940. As noted by ACR, including lags into their regression and lacking data prior to 1900, CM essentially shorten their analysis period to 1905 to 1936. Another difference in the data used is the number of cities investigated. CM look at 13 cities, limited by availability of implementation dates whereas ACR look at a larger sample of 25 cities. These variations in their data had little impact on the

Table 2

Water Filtration Dates

CM cities	CM	ACR
Baltimore	1914	1915
Chicago	>1940	
Cincinnati	1907	1907
Cleveland	1917	1918
Detroit	1923	1923
Jersey City	1978	
Louisville	1910	1909
Memphis	>1936	
Milwaukee	1939	1939
New Orleans	1909	1909
Philadelphia	1908	1906
Pittsburgh	1908	1908
St. Louis	1915	1915

demographics (Table 1), which is reassuring when comparing their results. ACR and CM did

disagree on the use of several implementation dates used in their analysis. CM provide a convincing comment on this issue, noting some mistakes but also conducting sensitivity analysis that show the dates do not substantially impact their results. Additionally, Table 2 shows how these dates are not massively dissimilar only varying by a maximum of 2 years in Philadelphia.

CM regression equation

$$1. \ln m_{c,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Filter}_{c,t} + \beta_2 \text{Chlorine}_{c,t} + \beta_3 \text{Filter}_{c,t} \times \text{Chlorine}_{c,t} + \delta_c + \mu_t + \gamma_c l_{c,t} + \sum \rho_d d_{d,c,t} + \sum \lambda_k \ln(m_{c,t-k}) + \varepsilon_{c,t}$$

ACR Regression equation

$$2. \ln m_{c,t} = \beta_0 + Z_{ct} \beta_1 + X_{ct} \beta_2 + v_c + w_t + \Theta_{ct} + \varepsilon_{ct}$$

The above equations show fairly similar regressions. AM include filtration, chlorination and clean water projects into the Z_{ct} term which CM incorporate in separate terms (equation 1). Both utilise city and year fixed effect terms and city time trends and demographic characteristics. CM also include a lagged mortality term and an interaction term between filtration and chlorine. The inclusion of the lagged mortality acknowledges how past mortality

Table 3

	Anderson et all	Cutler and Miller
Total Mortality		
Filtration	-2%	-14.80%
	Insignificant	Significant
Chlorination	1%	-2%
	Insignificant	Insignificant
Infant Mortality		
Filtration	-12.30%	-35%
	Significant	Significant
Chlorination	-7.70%	8.80%
	Insignificant	Insignificant

rates influence current rates, considering historical health conditions and could explain some

of the difference between CM and ACR's results, however it reduces CM's degrees of freedom and could also result in overfitting, explaining their larger estimates. Their dependent variable is fairly consistent between the papers, each looking at total, infant and typhoid mortality, both add detail on other diseases such as Pneumonia (CM) and Diarrhoea (ACR).

Key results obtained by CM and ACR are compared in Table 3. Notably, ACR did not find the relationship between filtration and total mortality to be significant. They only found that it had a substantial effect on infant mortality rates. Contrastingly, the filtration estimates from CM's analysis found that during the period of interest, filtration is associated with a 14.8% fall in total mortality rates and overall clean water technologies account for 43% of the mortality decline between 1900 and 1936, suggesting a substantial contribution of clean water interventions to the mortality transition. The revised analysis in Cutler and Miller (2022) reduces this to 38%, still allowing them to suggest clean water intervention as a policy tool, whereas ACR instead reject the role of these interventions and suggest nutrition and standard of living, requiring further analysis. The equivalent filtration estimate for ACR is only 2% and is insignificant. The discrepancy in the estimates suggest a lower impact of the interventions on mortality in ACR's findings. There could be several reasons for this including their methods, fundamental differences in the data because of the large sample size in ACR. ACR added cities which could lead to unobservable differences which affected the effectiveness of public health interventions. It is also possible that the effectiveness of filtration or other interventions may vary across cities. Unlike CM, ACR investigate a broader range of public health interventions where CM focus on filtration and chlorination. They look at clean water projects, sewage treatment plants, and clean milk efforts in a number of cities. Whilst these are not found to have significantly affect total mortality, their analysis provides a broader view of whether public health interventions were a driver of the fall in mortality.

Despite these differences, where the findings are significant in both papers, they do not contradict in trend direction. Both papers are most aligned in their conclusions on the effect of clean water interventions on typhoid mortality. ACR found that filtration is associated with a 16% pt reduction in typhoid mortality and CM's estimate is 15% pt. Therefore, whilst they disagree on the effectiveness of clean water interventions in total mortality, they agree that they were important in the reduction of mortality from water borne diseases.

CM argue that their results explain between 43% (or 38% in the comment) of the decline in mortality during their period of investigation, however ACR dispute this and believe other factors notably standard of living and nutrition should be further investigated as potential drivers during the period. Chapman (2019) studied British urban mortality and found that government investment explained up to 60% of the decline in urban mortality between 1861 and 1900. So, it is likely that these public health interventions played some role in reducing mortality, but that the slightly different methods and substantially larger sample size of ACR led to different conclusions. Additionally, it is important to note that the decline only covers a short period since the mid-18th century. Davenport et al (2011) investigated the decline in the early 1800s due to the smallpox vaccine and it is likely that other medical interventions played a role such as the development of antibiotics in the 1940s (Cutler et al 2006).

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